

Legendre inversions and Ultra-hypergeometric series identities

Basen Wuyungaowa*

Department of Mathematics, College of Sciences and Technology,
Inner Mongolia University
Huhhot 010021, P. R. China

Abstract

In this paper, we extension of hypergeometric series to obtain a new Ultra-hypergeometric series, we establish three terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identities, by means of Legendre inverse series relations. By using the linear combination between these three identities, we can obtain new terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identities.

Keywords : Ultra-hypergeometric series; Legendre inversions; convolution formula.

1 Introduction

For complex number x and a natural number n , denote the α -shifted-factorial by(see[5])

$$\langle x|\alpha\rangle_0 = 1, \langle x|\alpha\rangle_n = x(x - \alpha)(x - 2\alpha) \cdots (x - n\alpha + \alpha), \quad (1)$$

$$(x|\alpha)_0 = 1, (x|\alpha)_n = x(x + \alpha)(x + 2\alpha) \cdots (x + n\alpha - \alpha). \quad (2)$$

Evidently, the classical shifted-factorial is $\alpha = 1$

$$\langle x\rangle_0 = 1, \langle x\rangle_n = x(x - 1)(x - 2) \cdots (x - n + 1),$$

$$(x)_0 = 1, (x)_n = x(x + 1)(x + 2) \cdots (x + n - 1).$$

By formula (1) we give the following definition.

Definition 1 For $(x, y) \in C^2$, let us denote

$$\binom{x}{y} \Big| \alpha = \begin{cases} \frac{\langle x|\alpha\rangle_y}{y!}, & x \in C^2, y \in N \\ 0, & x \in C^2, y \notin N \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

* Corresponding author

E-mail address: 1084714224@qq.com(Basen); wuyungw@163.com(Wuyungaowa).

In particular, it is obvious that the binomial coefficients are given by $\alpha = 1, x, y \in N$,

$$\binom{n}{k} = \frac{\langle n \rangle_k}{k!} = \frac{n(n-1)(n-2) \cdots (n-k+1)}{k!}.$$

Although we have two kinds of identities by Definition 1

$$\binom{x+n\alpha}{n-k} \Big| \alpha = \frac{(\alpha+x|\alpha)_n}{(n-k)!(\alpha+x|\alpha)_k}, \tag{4}$$

$$\binom{x+n\alpha}{\varepsilon+n+k} \Big| \alpha = (-1)^{(\varepsilon+k)} \frac{(\alpha+x|\alpha)_n (-x|\alpha)_{k+\varepsilon}}{(\varepsilon+n+k)!}. \tag{5}$$

Next, we give the definition of α -hypergeometric series.

Definition 2 A Ultra-hypergeometric series is a series $\sum c_n$, such that c_{n+1}/c_n is a rational function of n . On factorizing the polynomials in n , we obtain

$$\frac{c_{n+1}}{c_n} = \frac{(a_1+n\alpha_1)(a_2+n\alpha_2) \cdots (a_p+n\alpha_p)z}{(b_1+n\beta_1)(b_2+n\beta_2) \cdots (b_q+n\beta_q)(n+1)}, \tag{6}$$

from (6), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n = c_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1|\alpha_1)_n (a_2|\alpha_2)_n \cdots (a_p|\alpha_p)_n z^n}{(b_1|\beta_1)_n (b_2|\beta_2)_n \cdots (b_q|\beta_q)_n n!} = c_0 {}_pF_q \left(\begin{matrix} (a_1|\alpha_1), (a_2|\alpha_2), \dots, (a_p|\alpha_p) \\ (b_1|\beta_1), (b_2|\beta_2), \dots, (b_q|\beta_q) \end{matrix} ; z \right).$$

Here the b_i are not a non-negative integer multiple of β_i or zero, as that would make denominator zero.

For typographical reasons, we shall sometimes denote the sum on the right side of (7) by ${}_pF_q((a_1|\alpha_1), (a_2|\alpha_2), \dots, (a_p|\alpha_p); (b_1|\beta_1), (b_2|\beta_2), \dots, (b_q|\beta_q); z)$ or by ${}_pF_q$.

In particular, in formula (7) when $\alpha_i = \beta_i = 1$ is classical hypergeometric series (see[1,2,3])

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n = c_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1)_n (a_2)_n \cdots (a_p)_n z^n}{(b_1)_n (b_2)_n \cdots (b_q)_n n!} = c_0 {}_pF_q \left(\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_q \end{matrix} ; z \right).$$

Lemma 1[4] We can introduction Legendre two pairs inversions, let p be a fixed real number the follow inverse series relations hold:

$$f(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \binom{p+2n}{n-k} \frac{p+2k}{p+2n} g(k), \tag{8}$$

$$g(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \binom{p+n+k-1}{n-k} f(k). \tag{9}$$

We shall also use another pair of inversions

$$F(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \binom{p+2n}{n-k} G(k), \tag{10}$$

$$G(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \binom{p+n+k}{n-k} \frac{p+2n}{p+n+k} F(k), \tag{11}$$

this follows directly from the replacements

$$F(k) = (p+2k)f(k), \text{ and } G(k) = (p+2k)g(k).$$

Lemma 2[5] For generalized Vandermonde convolution formula

$$\binom{x+y}{m} \Big| \alpha = \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{x}{k} \Big| \alpha \binom{y}{m-k} \Big| \alpha. \tag{12}$$

Especially $\alpha = 1$ is the Chu-vandermonde convolution formula(see[6])

$$\binom{x+y}{m} = \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{x}{k} \binom{y}{m-k}.$$

2 Terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identity

This section mainly uses the Legendre inversion relationship to give three useful Ultra-hypergeometric series identities.

Theorem 1 For $\delta = 0, 1$ terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identity

$$\begin{aligned} & {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n+1+\delta, (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha+c|\alpha), (\alpha+a-c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\ &= \frac{n!}{(a-2c)(\alpha-a|\alpha)_{\delta+1}(\delta+1)_n} \left\{ \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{n+1+\delta}}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} - \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_{n+1+\delta}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof Applying lemma 2 it is not difficult to show that

$$\frac{a-2c}{a+2n\alpha} \binom{a+2n\alpha}{\delta+1+2n} \Big| \alpha = \sum_{k=0}^{\delta+1+2n} \frac{\delta+1+2n-2k}{\delta+1+2n} \binom{c+n\alpha}{k} \Big| \alpha \binom{a-c+n\alpha}{\delta+1+2n-k} \Big| \alpha.$$

In the above formula, then for $\delta = 0, 1$, splitting the last sum into two parts and then performing replacements $k \rightarrow n-k$, $k \rightarrow \delta+1+n+k$, respectively, for the first and the second sum, we can manipulate the sum as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{a-2c}{a+2n\alpha} \binom{a+2n\alpha}{\delta+1+2n} \Big| \alpha &= \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^n + \sum_{k=\delta+1+n}^{\delta+1+2n} \right\} \frac{\delta+1+2n-2k}{\delta+1+2n} \binom{c+n\alpha}{k} \Big| \alpha \binom{a-c+n\alpha}{\delta+1+2n-k} \Big| \alpha \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{\delta+1+2k}{\delta+1+2n} \left\{ \binom{c+n\alpha}{n-k} \Big| \alpha \binom{a-c+n\alpha}{\delta+1+n+k} \Big| \alpha - \binom{c+n\alpha}{n-k} \Big| \alpha \binom{a-c+n\alpha}{\delta+1+n+k} \Big| \alpha \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Applying (4), (5) it is not difficult to binomial coefficient identity

$$\frac{(2c-a)(a|\alpha)_{2n}(\alpha-a|\alpha)_{\delta}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{\delta+1+2n}{n-k} \frac{\delta+1+2k}{\delta+1+2n} \left\{ \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_{k+\delta+1}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_k} - \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{k+\delta+1}}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_k} \right\},$$

the last identity matches (8) $p = \delta + 1$ and

$$\begin{aligned} f(n) &= \frac{(2c-a)(a|\alpha)_{2n}(\alpha-a|\alpha)_{\delta}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n}, \\ g(k) &= \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_{k+\delta+1}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_k} - \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{k+\delta+1}}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_k}. \end{aligned}$$

The dual relation corresponding to (9) gives us the following identity

$$\frac{(c-a|\alpha)_{n+\delta+1}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n} - \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{n+\delta+1}}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{\delta+n+k}{n-k} \frac{(2c-a)(a|\alpha)_{2k}(\alpha-a|\alpha)_{\delta}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_k(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_k}.$$

Rewriting the binomial coefficient in terms of factions(see[7])

$$\binom{\delta+n+k}{n-k} = (-1)^k \frac{(\delta+1)_n}{n!} \frac{(-n)_k(\delta+1+n)_k}{(\delta+1)_{2k}},$$

So, we easily find the following terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identity:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n+1+\delta, (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha) \\ \frac{1}{2}+\delta, \alpha+c|\alpha, \alpha+a-c|\alpha \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= \frac{n!}{(a-2c)(\alpha-a|\alpha)_\delta(\delta+1)_n} \left\{ \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{n+1+\delta}}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} - \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_{n+1+\delta}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n} \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2 In Theorem 1, when $\alpha = 1$, for $\delta = 0, 1$, we have terminating balanced hypergeometric series identity:

$${}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n+1+\delta, \frac{a}{2}, \frac{a+1}{2} \\ \delta+\frac{1}{2}, c, 1+a-c \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) = \frac{n!}{(\delta+1)_n(a-2c)(1-a)_\delta} \left\{ \frac{(-c)_{n+1+\delta}}{(1+a-c)_n} - \frac{(c-a)_{n+1+\delta}}{(1+c)_n} \right\}.$$

this is the corollary of Theorem 1 in the Reference [7].

Corollary 3 In Theorem 1, when $\alpha = 0$ and $\delta = 0$ we can establish generating functions identity as follows:

$$\Psi(1, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-n)_k (1+\delta+n)_k (\frac{a}{2})^{2k} 1 t^n}{(\delta+\frac{1}{2})_k [c(a-c)]^k k! n!} = \frac{c}{2c-a} \exp\left(\frac{c}{c-a}t\right) - \frac{c-a}{a-2c} \exp\left(\frac{c-a}{c}t\right).$$

Theorem 4 For $\delta = 0, 1$ terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identity

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n+\delta, (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta+\frac{1}{2}, (\alpha+c|\alpha), (\alpha+a-c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= \begin{cases} \frac{a-2c+2n\alpha}{2(a-2c)} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} + \frac{a-2c-2n\alpha}{2(a-2c)} \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n}, & \delta = 0 \\ \frac{1}{(1+2n)(\alpha-a)} \left\{ \frac{[a-2c+(1+2n)\alpha](-c|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(a-2c)(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} + \frac{[a-2c-(1+2n)\alpha](c-a|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(a-2c)(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n} \right\}, & \delta = 1 \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof Recall again applying lemma 2 it is not difficult to show that

$$\left(\begin{matrix} a+2n-\alpha \\ \delta+2n \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right) = \sum_{k=0}^{\delta+2n} \frac{\delta+a-2c+2n-2k}{a-2c} \left(\begin{matrix} c+n\alpha \\ \delta+2n-k \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right) \left(\begin{matrix} a-c+n\alpha \\ k \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right).$$

In the above formula then for $\delta = 1, 2$, splitting the last sum into two parts and then performing replacements $k \rightarrow n-k$, $k \rightarrow \delta+n+k$, respectively, for the first and the second sum, we can manipulate the sum as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\begin{matrix} a+2n\alpha-\alpha \\ \delta+2n \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right) + (1-\delta) \left(\begin{matrix} c+n\alpha \\ n \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right) \left(\begin{matrix} a-c+n\alpha \\ n \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right) \\
 &= \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^n + \sum_{k=\delta+n}^{\delta+2n} \right\} \frac{a-2c+(2n-2k+\delta)\alpha}{a-2c} \left(\begin{matrix} c+n\alpha \\ \delta+2n-k \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right) \left(\begin{matrix} a-c+n\alpha \\ k \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^n \left\{ \frac{a-2c+(2k+\delta)\alpha}{a-2c} \left(\begin{matrix} c+n\alpha \\ \delta+n+k \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right) \left(\begin{matrix} a-c+n\alpha \\ n-k \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \frac{a-2c-(2k+\delta)\alpha}{a-2c} \left(\begin{matrix} c+n\alpha \\ n-k \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right) \left(\begin{matrix} a-c+n\alpha \\ \delta+n+k \end{matrix} \middle| \alpha \right) \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Applying (4), (5) it is not difficult to binomial coefficient identity

$$\frac{(a|\alpha)_{2n}(\alpha - a|\alpha)_\delta}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_n(\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_n} + (1 - \delta) \binom{\delta + 2n}{n}$$

$$= \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{\delta + 2n}{n - k} \left\{ \frac{a - 2c + (\delta + 2k)\alpha}{a - 2c} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{k+\delta}}{(\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_k} + \frac{a - 2c - (\delta + 2k)\alpha}{a - 2c} \frac{(c - a|\alpha)_{k+\delta}}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_k} \right\},$$

the last identity matches (10) $p = \delta$ and

$$F(n) = \frac{(a|\alpha)_{2n}(\alpha - a|\alpha)_\delta}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_n(\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_n} + (1 - \delta) \binom{\delta + 2n}{n},$$

$$G(k) = \left\{ \frac{a - 2c + (\delta + 2k)\alpha}{a - 2c} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{k+\delta}}{(\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_k} + \frac{a - 2c - (\delta + 2k)\alpha}{a - 2c} \frac{(c - a|\alpha)_{k+\delta}}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_k} \right\}.$$

The dual relation corresponding to (11) gives us the following identity

$$\frac{a - 2c + (\delta + 2n)\alpha}{a - 2c} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{n+\delta}}{(\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_n} - \frac{a - 2c - (\delta + 2n)\alpha}{a - 2c} \frac{(c - a|\alpha)_{n+\delta}}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_n}$$

$$= \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{\delta + n + k}{n - k} \frac{\delta + 2n}{\delta + n + k} \left\{ \frac{(a|\alpha)_{2k}(\alpha - a|\alpha)_\delta}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_k(\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_k} + (1 - \delta) \binom{2k}{k} \right\}.$$

The following expression for $\delta = 0, 1$ results is zero[see7]

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{\delta + n + k}{n - k} \frac{\delta + 2n}{\delta + n + k} (1 - \delta) \binom{2k}{k} = 0.$$

Hence we have the Ultra-hypergeometric series identity in Theorem 4.

Corollary 5 In Theorem 4, when $\alpha = 1$, for $\delta = 0, 1$ terminating 2-balanced hypergeometric series identity:

$${}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + \delta, \frac{a}{2}, \frac{a+1}{2} \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, 1 + c, 1 + a - c \end{matrix} ; 1 \right)$$

$$= \begin{cases} \frac{a - 2c + 2n}{a - 2c} \frac{(-c)_n}{(1 + a - c)_n} + \frac{a - 2c - 2n}{a - 2c} \frac{(c - a)_n}{(1 + c)_n}, & \delta = 0 \\ \frac{1}{(2n + 1)(1 - a)} \left\{ \frac{a - 2c + 1 + 2n}{a - 2c} \frac{(-c)_{n+1}}{(1 + a - c)_n} + \frac{a - 2c - (2n + 1)}{a - 2c} \frac{(c - a)_{n+1}}{(1 + c)_n} \right\}, & \delta = 1 \end{cases}$$

this is the corollary of Theorem 1 in the Reference [7].

Corollary 6 In Theorem 4 when $\alpha = 0$ and $\delta = 0$ we can established generating functions identity as follows:

$$\Psi(1, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-n)_k (n)_k \left(\frac{a}{2}\right)^{2k}}{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)_k [c(a - c)]^k} \frac{1}{k!} \frac{t^n}{n!} = \frac{1}{2} \exp\left(\frac{c}{c - a} t\right) + \frac{1}{2} \exp\left(\frac{c - a}{c} t\right).$$

Theorem 7 For $\delta = 0, 1$ terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identity

$${}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, \delta + n, \left(\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha\right), \left(\alpha + \frac{a}{2}|\alpha\right) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right)$$

$$= \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_n} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(c - a|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_n}, & \delta = 0 \\ \frac{1}{a(1 + 2n)} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_n} + \frac{1}{a(1 + 2n)} \frac{(c - a|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_n}, & \delta = 1 \end{cases}$$

Proof Recall again applying lemma 2 it is not difficult to show that

$$\binom{a + 2n\alpha}{\delta + 2n} \Big| \alpha = \sum_{k=0}^{\delta+2n} \binom{c + n\alpha}{\delta + 2n - k} \Big| \alpha \binom{a - c + n\alpha}{k} \Big| \alpha.$$

In the above formula then for $\delta = 1, 2$, splitting the last sum into two parts and then performing replacements $k \rightarrow n - k, k \rightarrow \delta + n + k$, respectively, for the first and the second sum, we can manipulate the sum as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} & \binom{a + 2n\alpha}{\delta + 2n} \Big| \alpha + (1 - \delta) \binom{c + n\alpha}{n} \Big| \alpha \binom{a - c + n\alpha}{n} \Big| \alpha \\ &= \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^n + \sum_{k=\delta+n}^{\delta+2n} \right\} \binom{c + n\alpha}{\delta + 2n - k} \Big| \alpha \binom{a - c + n\alpha}{k} \Big| \alpha \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n \left\{ \binom{c + n\alpha}{\delta + n + k} \Big| \alpha \binom{a - c + n\alpha}{n - k} \Big| \alpha + \binom{c + n\alpha}{n - k} \Big| \alpha \binom{a - c + n\alpha}{\delta + n + k} \Big| \alpha \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Recall again applying (4), (5) it is not difficult to binomial coefficient identity

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{(\alpha + a|\alpha)_{2n} (a|\alpha)_{\delta}}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_n (\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_n} + (1 - \delta) \binom{\delta + 2n}{n} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{\delta + 2n}{n - k} \left\{ \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{k+\delta} (-1)^{\delta}}{(\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_k} - \frac{(c - a|\alpha)_{k+\delta} (-1)^{\delta}}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_k} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

the last identity matches (10) $p = \delta$ and

$$\begin{aligned} F(n) &= \frac{(\alpha + a|\alpha)_{2n} (a|\alpha)_{\delta}}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_n (\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_n} + (1 - \delta) \binom{\delta + 2n}{n}, \\ G(k) &= \left\{ \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{k+\delta} (-1)^{\delta}}{(\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_k} + \frac{(c - a|\alpha)_{k+\delta} (-1)^{\delta}}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_k} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

The dual relation corresponding to (11) given us the following identity

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{n+\delta} (-1)^{\delta}}{(\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_n} + \frac{(c - a|\alpha)_{n+\delta} (-1)^{\delta}}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_n} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \frac{\delta + 2n}{\delta + n + k} \binom{\delta + n + k}{n - k} \left\{ \frac{(\alpha + a|\alpha)_{2k} (a|\alpha)_{\delta}}{(\alpha + c|\alpha)_k (\alpha + a - c|\alpha)_k} + (1 - \delta) \binom{\delta + 2k}{k} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

The following expression for $\delta = 0, 1$ results is zero[see7]

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{\delta + n + k}{n - k} \frac{\delta + 2n}{\delta + n + k} (1 - \delta) \binom{2k}{k} = 0.$$

Hence we have the Ultra-hypergeometric series identity in Theorem 7.

Corollary 8 In Theorem 7, when $\alpha = 1$, for $\delta = 0, 1$, we have terminating balanced hypergeometric series identity:

$${}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, \delta + n, \frac{a+1}{2}, 1 + \frac{a}{2} \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, 1 + c, 1 + a - c \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{(-c)_n}{(1 + a - c)_n} + \frac{(c - a)_n}{(1 + c)_n} \right\}, & \delta = 0 \\ \frac{1}{a(1 + 2n)} \frac{(-c)_{n+1}}{(1 + a - c)_n} + \frac{1}{a(1 + 2n)} \frac{(c - a)_{n+1}}{(1 + c)_n}, & \delta = 1 \end{cases}$$

3 Linear combinations and related Ultra-hypergeometric formulae

This section mainly uses the linear combination between the three theorems in the previous section to obtain new terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identities.

Theorem 9 For $\delta = 0, 1$ terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identity

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_5F_4 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + \delta, (n + \delta|\alpha), (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (n + \delta|\alpha), (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= \begin{cases} \left\{ \frac{(1-\alpha)(a-2c+2n\alpha)}{2(a-2c)} + \frac{(-c+n\alpha)\alpha}{(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} \right\} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} + \left\{ \frac{(1-\alpha)(a-2c-2n\alpha)}{2(a-2c)} - \frac{(c-a+n\alpha)\alpha}{(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} \right\} \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n}, & \delta = 0 \\ \left\{ \frac{(1-\alpha)(a-2c+2n\alpha)}{(2n+1)(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} + \frac{(-c+n\alpha+\alpha)\alpha}{(a-2c)(n+1)(\alpha-a|\alpha)_2} \right\} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} + \left\{ \frac{(1-\alpha)(a-2c-2n\alpha-\alpha)}{(2n+1)(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} - \frac{(c-a+n\alpha+\alpha)\alpha}{(a-2c)(n+1)(\alpha-a|\alpha)_2} \right\} \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n}, & \delta = 1 \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof Because

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_5F_4 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + \delta, (\delta + n + \alpha|\alpha), (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\delta + n|\alpha)(\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= (1 - \alpha) {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + \delta, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) + \alpha {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + 1 + \delta, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

We then use Theorem 1 and Theorem 4 to immediately get the conclusion of Theorem 9.

Theorem 10 For $\delta = 0, 1$ terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identity

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_5F_4 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n, 2n + 1 + \delta, (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha) \\ \frac{1}{2}, 2n + \delta, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= \begin{cases} \left\{ \frac{a-2c+2n\alpha}{4(a-2c)} + \frac{-c+n\alpha}{2(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} \right\} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} + \left\{ \frac{a-2c-2n\alpha}{4(a-2c)} - \frac{c-a+n\alpha}{2(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} \right\} \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n}, & \delta = 0 \\ \left\{ \frac{a-2c+(2n+1)\alpha}{2(1+2n)(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} + \frac{-c+n\alpha+\alpha}{2(n+1)(a-2c)(\alpha-a|\alpha)_2} \right\} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} + \left\{ \frac{a-2c-(2n+1)\alpha}{2(2n+1)(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} - \frac{c-a+n\alpha+\alpha}{2(n+1)(a-2c)(\alpha-a|\alpha)_2} \right\} \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n}, & \delta = 1 \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof Because

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_5F_4 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + \delta, (n + \delta|\alpha), (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (n|\alpha)(\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + \delta, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) + \frac{1}{2} {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + 1 + \delta, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

We then use Theorem 1 and Theorem 4 to immediately get the conclusion of Theorem 10.

Theorem 11 For $\delta = 0, 1$ terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identity

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_5F_4 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + \delta, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha), (2(n + \delta)a + [a + 2(n + \delta)\alpha]|a + 2(n + \delta)\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha), (2(n + \delta)a|a + 2(n + \delta)\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= \begin{cases} \left\{ \frac{-c+n\alpha}{2(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} + \frac{1}{4} \right\} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} + \left\{ \frac{1}{4} - \frac{c-a+n\alpha}{2(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} \right\} \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n}, & \delta = 0 \\ \left\{ \frac{-c+n\alpha+\alpha}{2(n+1)(a-2c)(\alpha-a|\alpha)_2} + \frac{1}{2a(2n+1)} \right\} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} + \left\{ \frac{1}{2a(2n+1)} - \frac{c-a+n\alpha+\alpha}{2(n+1)(a-2c)(\alpha-a|\alpha)_2} \right\} \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n}, & \delta = 1 \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof Because

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_5F_4 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + \delta, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha), (2(n + \delta)a + [a + 2(n + \delta)\alpha]|a + 2(n + \delta)\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha), ((n + \delta)a|a + 2(n + \delta)\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + 1 + \delta, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) + \frac{1}{2} {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + \delta, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\alpha + \frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

We then use Theorem 1 and Theorem 7 to immediately get the conclusion of Theorem 11.

Theorem 12 For $\delta = 0, 1$ terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identity

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_5F_4 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + \delta, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha), (a + \alpha|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha), (a|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= \begin{cases} \left\{ \frac{a-2c+2n\alpha}{4(a-2c)} + \frac{1}{4} \right\} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} + \left\{ \frac{a-2c-2n\alpha}{4(a-2c)} + \frac{1}{4} \right\} \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_n}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n}, & \delta = 0 \\ \left\{ \frac{a-2c+(2n+\alpha)}{2(2n+1)(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} + \frac{1}{2a(2n+1)} \right\} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} + \left\{ \frac{a-2c-(2n+1)\alpha}{2(2n+1)(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} + \frac{1}{2a(2n+1)} \right\} \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n}, & \delta = 1 \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof Because

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_5F_4 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, \delta + n, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha), (a + \alpha|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha), (a|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, \delta + n, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) + \frac{1}{2} {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, \delta + n, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\alpha + \frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \delta + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

We then use Theorem 4 and Theorem 7 to immediately get the conclusion of Theorem 12.

Corollary 13 In Theorem12,when $a = c = \alpha$ and $\delta = 0$ we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-n}{k} \binom{n}{k} = 0.$$

Theorem 14 Terminating Ultra-hypergeometric series identity

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_5F_4 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, n + 1, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha), (2a + \alpha|a + \alpha) \\ 1 + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha), (a|a + \alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= \left\{ \frac{1}{2(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} + \frac{1}{2a(2n+1)} \right\} \frac{(-c|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha+a-c|\alpha)_n} + \left\{ \frac{1}{2(a-2c)(\alpha-a)} + \frac{1}{a(2n+1)} \right\} \frac{(c-a|\alpha)_{n+1}}{(\alpha+c|\alpha)_n}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof Because

$$\begin{aligned}
 & {}_5F_4 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, 1 + n, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha), (a + \frac{\alpha}{2}|\frac{\alpha}{2}) \\ \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha), (a|\frac{\alpha}{2}) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, 1 + n, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right) + \frac{1}{2} {}_4F_3 \left(\begin{matrix} -n, 1 + n, (\frac{a+\alpha}{2}|\alpha), (\alpha + \frac{a}{2}|\alpha) \\ 1 + \frac{1}{2}, (\alpha + c|\alpha), (\alpha + a - c|\alpha) \end{matrix} ; 1 \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

In Theorem 1 when $\delta = 0$ and Theorem 7 when $\delta = 1$ to immediately get the conclusion of Theorem 14.

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